

PeCATHS

PHOTO-ELECTROCATALYTIC ROUTES
FOR LONG-TERM SUSTAINABLE
HYDROGEN STORAGE

<https://pecaths.eu/>

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PeCATHS is a four-year initiative adopting a holistic methodology to pioneer an innovative energy storage system that leverages hydrogen stored into LOHCs alongside biomass conversion. By conducting comprehensive life cycle assessments, PeCATHS aims to showcase the efficacy of transforming biomass into valuable chemicals, adhering to principles of the circular economy and utilizing environmentally benign raw materials.

PeCATHS is committed to developing an integrated long-term energy storage system utilizing hydrogen in the form of liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs), coupled with innovative biomass conversion. This approach enables the direct transfer of hydrogen from biomass to LOHCs without the hydrogen gas production, while simultaneously generating high-value chemicals.

By integrating chemical and energy sectors, the project aims to synthesize platform chemicals and achieve long-term energy storage in liquid form, enhancing both the sustainability and efficiency of energy systems. A major advantage of LOHC technology is its ability to transform hydrogen gas into a stable liquid energy carrier, significantly facilitating the storage, transport and distribution.

To tackle the economic challenges associated with this technology, PeCATHS employs a cost-effective strategy that utilizes biomass as a hydrogen source and solar power as a renewable energy source. This method allows for the direct integration of hydrogen into LOHCs without the complexities of gas compression and storage, thereby reducing costs and enhancing competitiveness against conventional energy storage systems.

PeCATHS addresses the critical need for sustainable and viable energy storage, transport, and distribution solutions through the use of advanced (photo)electrocatalytic transformations. This project not only aims to reduce operational costs but also seeks to contribute to the development of sustainable energy infrastructures vital for future energy networks.

There are different ways to store hydrogen and one interesting approach for massive implementation, long-term and low-cost storage, is the use of Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers as it has been proposed by the *European Clean Hydrogen Partnership*.

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs)

The liquid organic hydrogen carrier technology is based on the use of organic compounds that can convert and reconvert hydrogen into chemical bonds through chemical reactions. These chemical processes are hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactions mediated by catalysts. When compared with hydrogen storage in gaseous or solid forms, liquid hydrogen storage has important engineering advantages such as compatibility with the existing infrastructures and similar features as the common liquid fuels. Liquid hydrogen can be pumped for delivery and distribution which facilitates the large-scale implementation. Hydrogen transformations and the intrinsic properties of the organic carriers determine the efficiency of LOHCs as hydrogen storage materials.

There are different organic compounds that may act as hydrogen carriers, among them the most common are cycloalkanes, N-heterocycles and alcohols. The carrier dictates the properties of the LOHCs system and determines the potential application.

 Biomass transformations. Biomass is a potential alternative feedstock to fossil fuel reserves for the synthesis of initial platform chemicals. These reactions combined with the cathodic production of green hydrogen allow distributing between the two reactions capital and operational expenses (CAPEX and OPEX) associated to the hydrolysis (i.e. electricity accounts for >70% of OPEX), and simultaneously produce added-value products from natural feedstocks. These combined benefits have contributed to a large acceleration in the reduction of green hydrogen cost and the development of a sustainable green chemical industry. PeCATHS goes beyond the state of the art and instead of green hydrogen, produces green protons that are directly used for storing hydrogen into LOHCs. This will contribute to develop a new technology for accelerating the reduction of green hydrogen cost. In PeCATHS, biomass transformations are selected by availability but even more important is the formation of industrially relevant initial platform chemicals.

PeCATHS has direct impact in the development of ways to obtain affordable clean energy (SDG7) at the same time that fight against climate change (SDG13). The ways to reach these objectives will have impact in the promotion of green industry and the adaptation of infrastructures for green transport and large-scale energy storage (SDG9), the generation of quality and improvement of existing workplaces associated economic growth (SDG8). The adoption of responsible production means (SDG12) as PeCATHS technology will promote alliances between different sectors that will lead to reach a sustainable development (SDG17).

Finally, our approach will incise positively in SDGs 1, 2, 10 and 11 as it will create value at the bottom of primary sector helping to redistribute resources and investments to smaller and more sustainable communities in rural and poorly developed areas, reducing inequalities in developed countries and poverty and hunger in the less developed countries.

Stakeholders and end users: The use of LOCHS as fuel reservoir requires 2 tanks, one for the loaded LOHC and the other for the discharged one, and a reactor to catalyze the H₂ recovery reaction. In LNG propelled ships, the same number of elements are already installed: one tank for fuel, other tank for the LNG and a boiler to obtain the gas. Tanks for LOHC need to be 1.9 times larger than for LNG as the useful energy they can provide is around 1.9 MWh/m³ (from 6.3 MWh/m³ stored energy), however these tanks do not need refrigeration at -160o what saves a large amount of energy and space of the insulation layers of the deposit. The same elements are needed in Trucks and cars. While trucks, especially long range, already incorporate two deposits, due to energy density of LOCHS, deposits would need 3-4 times more volume than fuel for the same distance. In cars also larger tanks are needed but their weight and the time for unloaded used LOCH and reloaded fresh LOCH will be much faster than for electric cars.

Impact

PeCATHS aims to revolutionize renewable hydrogen energy storage, through a novel technology that reduces the cost of green hydrogen production replacing water splitting by the combination of the (photo)electrochemical conversion of biomass and the direct storage of hydrogen in LOHCs. This approach produces valuable byproducts that allows sharing CAPEX and OPEX between the two processes and, at the same time, reduces CO₂ emissions by substituting fossil fuel-based chemicals by biomass derivatives. This technology has the potential to accelerate the energy transition much earlier than 2050 as it will keep energy prices low, a crucial aspect for a fast decarbonization of our society.

The impacts expected by the project may be classified according to the following levels of influence:

Scientific: The understanding of the mechanisms that control the reactions proposed is still limited. PeCATHS approach combining fundamental modelling with advanced structural, materials and (photo) electrochemical characterization (Output 4) will open new pathways for cross fertilization between concepts and measurements, to reach a more advanced stage of comprehension of the materials, kinetics and selectivity of the reactions. This will have a key impact in the development and optimization of the different (photo)electrodes and reactions proposed (Outputs 1 & 2) and especially when integrating all these elements in a single device (Outputs 3 & 5).

Economic/technological: the project proposes new photoelectrochemical and electrochemical configurations with the potential to make economically and environmentally sustainable the transition to an hydrogen based economy (Output 5). The different configurations proposed will allow both decentralized and intensive ways of storing huge amounts of hydrogen into known, cheap and easy to handle liquids (Output 4). PeCATHS concepts success will open the path to the design of the combination of other chemical reactions that complete the transition towards a green chemical industry and to supply the enormous amount of hydrogen needed to complete the energy transition.

Societal: PeCATHS approach will show the path to eliminate fossil fuel dependence on both energy and chemical industry, without the need of heavy subsidies that block the transition towards a zero or even negative CO₂ emission society. The use of biomass as a source to obtain hydrogen will involve the primary sector (forestry, agricultural) as a new ally to fight and reverse climate change at the same time that it increases its productivity. Generating scale economies in underpopulated agricultural and forestry areas of Europe will provide an opportunity to rebalance economic and population distribution between rural and urban areas. Other players of the primary sector (farming, agroindustry) may benefit from PeCATHS concepts after adapting the process to their specific biomass residuals.

CONSORTIUM

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